

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B286
Date: 24 April 2007
Take Off: 04:30:43
Landing: 09:53:00
Flight Time: 5h22m17

Campaign: IASI – A -Train

Operating Area: Gulf of Mexico

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Jon Taylor	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
6	Cloud Physics	Paul James	FAAM
7	AVAPS / Core Chem / CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM
8	ARIES	Joss Kent	Met Office
9	MARSS / Wet Neph / PSAP	Chawn Harlow	Met Office
10	AMS	Will Morgan	University of Manchester
11	CVI / FWVS	Jeff Brown	Met Office
12	Mission Scientist 2	Alessio Bozzo	University of Bologna
14			
15			
16			
17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B286 Track 24-APR-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B286
 Date: 24 April 2007
 Project: IASI
 Location: Gulf of Mexico

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
042112		Start-Up	-.10 kft	358	29'36.23N 95'10.06W
042403		ASP	-.10 kft	000	Open
043043		T/O	0.70 kft	180	
050752	052728	Profile 1	21.0 - 1.1 kft	111	
051702		QNH	12.2 kft	106	1020
052700		QNH	1.6 kft	105	1024
052939	060029	Run 1	1.1 kft	185	
060352	061243	Profile 2	1.1 - 9.7 kft	020	
061243	062921	Run 2	9.7 kft	014	
063309	064939	Profile 3	9.7 - 26.0 kft	187	
064940	065750	Run 3.1	26.0 kft	196	
070046	072424	Run 3.1	26.0 kft	352	
070251		Note	26.0 kft	010	heading change
072319		Note	26.0 kft	038	heading change
072746	074909	Profile 4	26.0 - 35.0 kft	176	
075238		Sonde 1	35.0 kft	000	
075338	081350	Run 4.1	35.0 kft	354	
080301		Sonde 2	35.0 kft	009	
081246		Sonde 3	35.0 kft	009	
081912	083520	Run 4.2	35.0 kft	195	
082804		Sonde 4	35.0 kft	191	
083634	085255	Run 4.3	35.0 kft	273	
083756		Sonde 5	35.0 kft	273	
084538		Sonde 6	35.0 kft	272	
085416	090916	Run 4.4	35.0 kft	354	
085416		Sonde 7	35.0 kft	354	
090139		Sonde 8	35.0 kft	355	
091018		Sonde 9	35.0 kft	295	
095300		Land	-.04 kft	178	
095458		ASP	-.04 kft	211	Closed
095829		Shutdown	-.04 kft	000	29'36.23N 95'10.06W

B286 Track 24-APR-07

96°W 95°W 94°W 93°W 92°W 91°W 90°W 89°W

96°W 95°W 94°W 93°W 92°W 91°W 90°W 89°W

Sortie Brief Gulf of Mexico

Flight B286

Tue 24th April 2007

Mission Scientist: Jonathan Taylor

Briefing: 2120L 0220Z

Take off: 2320L 0420Z

Land: 0445L 0945Z

Satellite overpass 08:03Z

Aim: To underfly Aqua and Cloudsat satellites in the Gulf of Mexico along the sub satellite track.

Location: Gulf of Mexico.

Weather conditions: Clear skies or Broken cloud.

Key instruments: ARIES, MARSS, AVAPS, Core Chem, Cloud Phys

Fixed Points: BAe 146 to follow fixed ground positions as follows:

Over GULF of MEXICO

Fixed point A: (28° N, 92°2' W)

Fixed point B: (28°N, 90° 10' W)

Fixed point C: (26°20' N, 90°10' W)

Fixed point D: (26°20'N, 92° 2'W)

Fixed point F: (28° N, 90°20' W)

Fixed point G: (26°20'N, 90° 47'W)

Fixed point I: (27°10' N, 90°33.5' W)

1. Take off from Houston and transit to point F to arrive at 1400ft (55 mins)
2. SLR from F to G at 1400ft (35mins)
3. Profile from G towards F at 1000ft/min to 10,000ft then SLR onwards to F at 10,000ft (35mins)
4. Profile from F towards G from 10,000ft to FL260 then continue on to G at FL260 (25 mins)
5. SLR from G to F at FL260 (20 mins)
6. Profile from F towards G from FL260 to FL350 (20mins)
7. SLR from G to F passing point I at 0803Z overpass during this run. Launch dropsonde at start of run, at overpass time and at end of run (20mins)
8. Fly point F to B to C to D to A at FL350 dropping sondes midway between B and C, at departing from C, midway C to D, on departing D, midway D to A and departing A
9. Transit back to Houston from point A (30mins)

B286 Mission Scientists Debrief Sheet.

Mission Scientist: Jonathan P Taylor.

The aim of this sortie was to study the cloud under an overpass of Cloudsat and Calipso over the Gulf of Mexico during the night. The AIRS instrument on the Aqua satellite also forms part of the A-train and its sub-satellite track was approximately 100nm to the East of the operating area. The BAe146 flew a pattern north-south along the line of the Cloudsat overpass with the WB-57 flying along the same track at 57,000ft.

The boundary layer was near saturation with a relative humidity of 98% and patchy cumulus clouds. The aerosol concentration in the boundary layer was high with the CNC giving concentrations in excess of 2000/cc. There were elevated layers of aerosol at around 7,000 to 10,000 and at 13,000ft. Significant biomass burning fires were known to be occurring in Mexico and GOES aerosol retrievals suggested that we might encounter this smoke. Initial in-flight analysis of the AMS data suggests that the smoke was not observed.

During the profile descent in to the area an extremely dry area was observed at around 5500ft (just at the top of the boundary layer) where dew point depressions nearing 50deg C were observed. A straight and level run was flown at 1400ft where the nephelometer scattering signature was seen to reverse from the normal situation to one where the red scattering was larger than the green or blue. During the low level run patchy cumulus were observed just above the aircraft. The SID probe picked up some aerosol particles. ARIES spectra indicated the presence of thin scattered cumulus and clear skies above that.

A profile was then flown from 1400ft to 10,000ft along the line of the sub-satellite track and this was followed by a run at 10,000ft. ARIES spectra at this level indicated thin cirrus and clear sky patches above with scattered cumulus below. Further profiles and straight and level runs were made at FL260 and FL350. The amount of cirrus seen by the naked eye in line of sight with the moon and by ARIES during zenith views increased during the flight. During the time of the overpass a series of dropsondes were launched. Subsequent analysis of the Cloudsat data showed that the cirrus was too thin for it to detect – it is expected that the cirrus will be seen by Calipso.

Following the run along the satellite track the BAE146 flew three legs of a box pattern at FL350 dropping sondes at the corners and at the mid track points. The WB57 flew along the same box viewing downwards with its interferometers. Once again ARIES spectra indicated a mixture of clear skies and cirrus clouds above.

This data set should be extremely useful for analysis of the ability of AIRS to detect very thin, possibly sub-visual cirrus, at night time. It should also be interesting to compare microphysics derived from the interferometer data with the observations from Calipso.

All in all a useful flight with some interesting challenging data for IR sounders.

05:25 - GE goes funny!
So dog can't keep up

07:40 - Divergence between GE & FWVS.

Ignore 1st end of 2nd start run 3.1 which is 3.2
IGNORABLE Sonde 3

" 1st end of run 4.1 (2nd start)

Sonde 7 @ Start of run 4.4

CVI hygrometer doesn't work w/ v. high RH of 98%
Cal on Hygman dodgy @ high altitude

15,000ft. - Seat belts sign On.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

J. TAYLOR

Flight No **B.286**
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Date **24/4/07**

Page **1** of **5**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
0430?					Thick climb into cloud. alt tops ≈ 7900ft 1017mb
					clouds clear above
044906	FL210		113		into moisture layer. halt @ FL210
045354		FL210	112	28°56'N 93°6'W	ALLES showing @ above. => quite thick. (no ocean signal)
045950		FL210	111	28°42'N 92°30'W	can see nigs below showing clear skies.
050752	P1	FL210 ↓	112		Start of P1 into area of operations.
051326	P7				still clear below
		14,500ft			Entered dry layer cool up from 200 → 1400/ce.
0521		7,520	106		Still in elevated aerosol layer
		7200ft			neph sat ↑ 22/21/14 B 6R
		6000ft			Aerosol layer decreasing NephSat 100
		5000ft			low point depressing 50deg!
		4720			Aerosol now increasing again
052728	P1	1400ft			End of P1
					neph satting inverted B 15 R G 6 B

Aircraft Scientist's Log

J. Thorne

Flight No **B.286**
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Date 26/4/07

Page 2 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
052935	R1	1400ft			Stg 1 run 1 pass F towards G. CNC ~ 2000/cc. PCASP = 300/cc Neph. Red = 69 Green = 60 Blue = 55
0535					RH = 98.63% at 1400ft AMS showing organic & sulphates => smoke plume? loadings low.
054207		1400ft			Same low level cloud just above
0547	R1	1400ft	188	26°56'N 90°36'W	ARIES shows low level cloud and then clear above this.
055430					SID probes picking up pths but not FTSSP or SW.
060023	R1	1400ft	186		End R1 at point G. Turn + then climb
	R2	1400ft			start of R2 pass 6 towards F to = 100kmb.
0604		2300ft			In patchy clear cloud Above 3000ft wet neph scattering = B > 50%
		5220ft			bit dry layer
		8600ft			8% neph scat ↑ CNC ↑.
061243	R2R2	1000ft	014		End of R2 + start of R2 RH 73% CNC = 1400/cc
				27N 90°31'W	ARIES showing clear above

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B 286**
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 Date 24/10/07

 Page 3 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
0619					ARIES seeing scattered cloud below.
0621	R2	10,000ft	013	27°26'N 90°24'W	ARIES showing cloud above QNH 1024
062636	R2	10,000ft	013	27°08'N 90°18'W	cloud below + above
062921	R2	10,000ft			End of run at Point F
063309	P3	10,000ft ↑			Start of P3 run 10,000ft to FL260 Some thin Ci visible around the run.
					AMS does not show wind biomass loss
063830		15,000ft			Entering dry layer CMC ↓ run 273 Neph scattering to zero. RAASP ≈ 20/cc
064806					ARIES seeing some patchy low level cloud.
064939	P3 R3	FL260	196	26°28'N 90°36'W	End of R3 @ FL260 today run F towards G.
065150		FL260	196	26°36'N 90°42'W	ARIES showing thin Ci above
065750	R3.1	FL260		26°06'N 90°56'W	End of R3.1 walkway put to
070116	R3.2	FL260	350		Start of R3.2 north of Pt G.
070256					ARIES seeing Ci above HDT change ∴ Increased roll.
		FL260	011		Now on hdy towards F
070938					ARIES showing Ci above
071533					Can see rags b'dy layer did either v. broken or gone.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

J. TAYLOR

Flight No **B. 286**
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Date **26/6/07**

Page **4** of **5**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
072247			026		Heading change
072626	R3-2	F2260	026		End of Run 3-2
072746	R4↑	F2260↑	176	28° 0' N 90° 18' W	Start of Profile 4 from F2260 Pk with point F.
072845					Turning on to pt F.
072934	R4↑	F2289	195°		
074909	Pk	F2350			End of P4 at Sounding Pt G. Turning.
075238	R4↑	F2350			Start of Run 4-1 from G to F. Sounding Pt G. Start of Run 4-1 Intermittent GPS.
					ARRIES ↓ holes clear skies.
080301	R4↑	F2350			P2 gone. Sounding
080301					Overpass at 0803 Z. just start of point I. 60 m away.
0804					Over point I.
081045	R4↑	F2350	009	29° 48' N 90° 18' W	ZDC picking up v. low clouds of ice pt I. T = -51.6 °C = -52.1 °C
081246	R4↑	F2350			Departure 3 gone. at Run
081350	R4↑	F2350	010		End of Run 4-1 now fly large box pattern.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

S Taylor

Flight No **B. 286**
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Date 26/6/07

Page 5 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
081912	R42	F2350	193		Start of Run from NE of B direct to C
082007		F2350		27° 48' N 89° 50' W	ARIES showing Ci above clear skies below.
082804		F2350	191	27° 6' N 90° 0' W	Launch Depende 4 ARIES showing clear above.
083121					ARIES seeing low cloud below.
083366					ARIES showing Ci above. 26° 27' 41" N at C 90° 8' 96" W
083520	R42	F2350			End R42 at point C
083634	R43	F2350	273°		Start Run for 3 from C to D
083756		F2350	273°		Launch Depende 5.
084130					ARIES showing Ci above
084322				26° 18' N 90° 56' W	ARIES showing clear above.
084538	R43	F2350	272	26° 18' N 91° 12' W	Launch Depende 6.
085255	R43	F2350			End Run for 3 at D
085416	R44	F2350	356		Start Run for 4 and launch of Depende 7 T = 51.28 Td = 51.63
085535					ARIES indicates clear skies above
090139		F2350			Launch Depende 8
090217					ARIES shows clear clear above.
090916	R44	F2350			End Run for 4

091028

Depende 9 gone
end of sunrise hasn't done

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number: B286****T/O: 043043****Date of flight:****Land: 095300**

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		
9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO		
a) Flight number: Bnnn	Y	NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful. X = Start = 043043 End = 095300 Time data processed to = 2dproc files present? *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat
b) Directory: PMSDATA:	Y	
c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i>	Y	
d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i>	Y	
e) TAS: Y	Y	
f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX	Y	
g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i>	Y	
h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i>	Y	
i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i>	Y	
j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5	Y	
k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud	Y	
l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown	Y	
m) Coefficient choice: 2	Y	
n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D	Y	
10) FLOODS> WAVE		Use PVWAVE for this section
i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D'		Error message about HDDR file should be ignored.
ii). exit		Records = 31
11) FLOODS> MODIFY		
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D	Y	X = Y = (X+1)
b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX	Y	
c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY	Y	
d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	Y	
12) CHECKS:		
Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i>		Correlated? y

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B286 **T/O:** 043043
Date of flight: 24-04-07 **Land:** 095300

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	Y	
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW	Y	
a) Flight number: Bnnn	Y	
b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT	Y	
c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP	Y	
Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary)	Y	
PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii)	Y	
d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i>	Y	Min size = 1
<i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value</i>	Y	
<i>of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i>	Y	
e) Calibration volume flow rate:	Y	Vol flow rate = 1.0
<i>Use the most recent value. 1.8ccs⁻¹</i>	Y	
<i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i>	Y	
<i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i>	Y	
f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D</i>	Y	
<i>processing stage 9d</i>	Y	
g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i>	Y	
h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>	Y	
3) FLOODS> WAVE		Use PVWAVE for this section
i). WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp'	y	
ii). WAVE> exit		
4) FLOODS> MODIFY		
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp	Y	
b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX	Y	
c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY	Y	MFDC
d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>	Y	
5) CHECKS		
Are PCASP and NEPH peaks synchronous?	?	
<i>In flight_plot, parameters</i>		
<i>Neph total blue scatter</i>		
<i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>		

FAAM Dropsonde Flight Log

Flight No.	B286	Date	24 Apr 2007
Page No.	1 of 2	Operator	Doug Anderson

GMT	Sonde No.	Event	Comments
		<i>e.g. launch, splashdown</i>	<i>e.g. wind data? PTH data? Lat/Long NB strings of dropsonde data contain: time, pressure hPa, T deg C, RH %, wind direction deg, wind speed m/s, longitude, latitude, height m</i>
07:52:42	1	Launch	238.10 -51.20 57.09 322.00 11.80 -21.10 -90.780000 26.133400 10676.80
08:05:21	1	splashdown	.01 1016.28 22.98 76.78 142.35 11.07 - 11.63 -90.777632 26.133093 99999.00 Launched at Point G NB. This sonde was opened and resealed on 21 Apr 2007 (B285) GPS started well but became intermittent after a few thousand feet but better again from around 20000'
08:03:57	2	Launch	238.10 -51.50 85.83 314.50 14.20 -16.70 -90.562000 27.153100 10676.30
08:15:11	2	splashdown	1016.68 23.42 79.97 143.97 10.88 - 11.24 -90.572894 27.072743 99999.00 Launched at Point I (Sat overpass) NB. This sonde was opened and resealed on 21 Apr 2007 (B285) GPS started well but became intermittent around 31000' but better again from around 14000'
08:12:51	3	Launch	238.10 -51.70 96.55 301.30 16.00 -17.30 -90.331200 28.005300 10676.50
08:25:22	3	splashdown	1017.52 22.65 79.42 142.27 7.94 - 7.59 -90.300405 28.012419 99999.00 Launched a little before Point F GPS started well but became intermittent around 31000' but better again from around 14000'
08:28:09	4	Launch	238.00 -51.30 65.23 282.20 16.40 -17.10 -90.049700 27.147100 10680.10
08:40:26	4	splashdown	1016.70 23.06 70.72 132.48 13.12 - 12.02 -90.036143 27.153888 99999.00 Launched mid way between Point B & C GPS started well but became intermittent around 28500' but better again from around '
08:37:57	5	Launch	238.00 -51.10 67.69 300.50 20.00 -16.70 -90.398500 26.334400 10677.70
08:50:44	5	splashdown	1017.05 23.10 70.25 132.05 11.73 - 11.81 -90.395243 26.334002 99999.00
08:45:42	6	Launch	238.30 -51.40 89.99 297.20 20.50 -17.10 -91.205100 26.336200 10671.70
08:58:33	6	splashdown	1016.04 23.04 77.10 137.63 11.26 - 11.33 -91.195835 26.340427 99999.00
08:54:18	7	Launch	238.20 -51.20 100.00 293.30 17.10 -16.60 -92.032200 26.431900 10674.00
09:06:55	7	splashdown	1015.60 23.14 83.90 146.49 10.30 - 11.07 -92.016608 26.438725 99999.00

Flight No.	B286	Date	24 Apr 2007
Page No.	2 of 2	Operator	Doug Anderson

GMT	Sonde No.	Event	Comments
		<i>e.g. launch, splashdown</i>	<i>e.g. wind data? PTH data? Lat/Long NB strings of dropsonde data contain: time, pressure hPa, T deg C, RH %, wind direction deg, wind speed m/s, longitude, latitude, height m</i>
09:02:06	8	Launch	238.00 -51.40 82.85 286.90 13.80 -16.50 -92.032900 27.207000 10679.00
09:14:21	8	splashdown	1016.34 22.78 87.65 148.77 8.16 - 11.41 -92.006844 27.185212 99999.00
09:10:21	9	Launch	238.20 -51.70 94.31 276.80 18.30 -15.80 -92.096700 28.028200 10674.10
09:22:57	9	splashdown	1017.68 22.97 88.33 151.92 7.55 - 11.44 -92.050787 28.055466 99999.00

B286 CVI log

4/23/07 4:38:27 PM
 4/23/07 4:38:50 PM Few test zeros on climb out
 4/23/07 4:47:25 PM 6.3Km test zero
 4/23/07 4:48:20 PM test zero at 6.4km
 4/23/07 4:53:45 PM test zero at 6.4km
 4/23/07 5:00:02 PM zero at 6.4KM
 4/23/07 5:05:46 PM zero at 6.4km
 4/23/07 5:13:34 PM zero at 4.7km
 4/23/07 5:16:20 PM zero at 3.9km
 4/23/07 5:17:49 PM flow adjusted prior to opening ro valvehyg
 4/23/07 5:18:10 PM flow adjusted prior to opening hygro valve
 4/23/07 5:19:21 PM zero at 3.0km
 4/23/07 5:21:41 PM zero at 2.3km
 4/23/07 5:24:00 PM zero at 1.5km
 4/23/07 5:26:24 PM zero at 0.7km
 4/23/07 5:27:30 PM end of profile descent
 4/23/07 5:29:00 PM zero at 350m
 4/23/07 5:29:48 PM start of run 1.1 at 1400ft
 4/23/07 5:34:14 PM zero at 1400ft slr
 4/23/07 5:39:10 PM zero at 1400ft slr
 4/23/07 5:44:04 PM zero at 1400ft slr
 4/23/07 5:49:43 PM zero at 1400ft slr
 4/23/07 5:55:08 PM zero at 1400ft slr
 4/23/07 6:00:01 PM zero at end of run at 1400ft (1.1)
 4/23/07 6:00:31 PM end of run 1.1
 4/23/07 6:04:20 PM start of profile 2 climb
 4/23/07 6:04:38 PM zero at 550m
 4/23/07 6:06:58 PM zero at 1.3km
 4/23/07 6:08:30 PM signal now much improved after leavin 98% rh
 4/23/07 6:09:24 PM zero at 2.0km
 4/23/07 6:12:06 PM zero at 2.8km
 4/23/07 6:12:53 PM end of profile climb and start of run 1.2
 4/23/07 6:15:51 PM rh73%
 4/23/07 6:17:08 PM zero at 2.965km slr
 4/23/07 6:22:11 PM zero at 2.965km slr
 4/23/07 6:27:08 PM zero at 2.965km slr
 4/23/07 6:29:34 PM end of run 2
 4/23/07 6:33:00 PM zero at 2.965km
 4/23/07 6:33:17 PM start of profile climb
 4/23/07 6:33:39 PM zero at 3.2km
 4/23/07 6:35:53 PM zero 3.8km
 4/23/07 6:38:03 PM zero at 4.4km
 4/23/07 6:40:32 PM zero at 5.2km
 4/23/07 6:43:01 PM zero at 6.0km
 4/23/07 6:45:45 PM zero at 6.8km
 4/23/07 6:48:07 PM zero at 7.5km
 4/23/07 6:49:54 PM end of profile 3 start or run 3
 4/23/07 6:51:03 PM zero at 7.93km slf
 4/23/07 6:56:09 PM zero at 7.93km slf
 4/23/07 6:57:57 PM end of run start of profile 4
 4/23/07 6:59:55 PM sorry - end of run and NOT start of profile 4
 4/23/07 7:01:17 PM zero at 7.93 start of run
 4/23/07 7:01:31 PM zero at 7.93 start of run 3.1
 4/23/07 7:01:48 PM zero at 7.93 start of run 3.2
 4/23/07 7:07:08 PM zero at 7.93km slr
 4/23/07 7:12:32 PM zero at 7.93km slr
 4/23/07 7:17:51 PM zero at 7.93km slr
 4/23/07 7:22:49 PM zero at 7.93km slr
 4/23/07 7:27:58 PM start of profile 4
 4/23/07 7:28:15 PM zero at 8.2km
 4/23/07 7:30:43 PM zero at 9.1km
 4/23/07 7:33:16 PM zero at 9.6km
 4/23/07 7:36:25 PM zero at 9,9km

ARIES flight log

Flight: B286 page 1 of

Date: 23/24 / 01/07 Operator(s): JOSS Res: 1 Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: IPSI HOUSTON GULF OF MEXICO FLIGHT.

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
024733	STARTED		ASCII				Hourly copying.
025632	Ground cal				70-71	30-46	
044842	Transit	1/60		disc			col/lat Sci
045829	Transit	1/60		disc	70-86	30-80	col/lat cal
045945	un	600/1	Zen	open	70-60	30-77	
050525	u	1/60	Cal	disc	70-64	30-60	
050816	Profile	1/60	Cal	disc	70-69	30-72	
050930	u u		Prof	open	70-31	30-52	Profile ZHCNCHZ-D
052916	end P1	1/60	Cal	disc	70-78	30-88	
053030	P1	600/1	NW	disc	70-92	30-85	
053910	P1	1/60	Cal	disc	70-96	30-85	
053919	P1	600/1	NW	disc	70-79	30-66	
054242	P1	1/60	Cal	disc	71-09	30-95	
054603	P1	240/1	Zen	open			Clear above.
054819	P1	360/1	NW	disc	70-87	31-55	
055126	P1	1/60	Cal	disc	70-74	31-48	
055243	P1	600/1	NW	disc	70-88	31-55	
055745	P1	1/60	Cal	disc	71-04	31-53	
055904	P1	120/1	Zen	open	70-41	31-18	
060049	end P1	1/60	Cal	disc	71-07	32-07	
060334	P2						Profile script.
061249	P2	1/60	Cal	disc	71-09	33-67	
061413	P2	300/1	Zen	open	70-46	33-76	
061650	P2	300/1	NW	disc	71-00	33-22	
061929	P2	1/60	Cal	disc	70-74	32-76	
062047	P2	300/1	Zen	open	70-18	32-04	
062330	P2	300/1	NW	disc	70-14	32-28	
062603	P2	1/60	Cal	disc	70-80	31-85	
062731	P2	240/1	Zen	open	70-3	31-38	
062935	P2	1/60	Cal	disc	70-98	31-36	

ARIES flight log

Flight: B286	page 2 of
Date: 23/04/07	Operator(s): Joss
Res: L	Gain A: 2B2
Loc./Notes:	

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
064912	R3-1	1/60	CW	CSD	7081	3074	
065109	R3-1	300/1	Zen	open	707	3067	
065351	R3-1	300/1	Nwd	CSD			
065628	R3-1	1/60	CW	CSD	7076	3067	
070042	R3-2	1/60	CW	CSD	7081	3075	
070212	R3-2	300/1	Zen	open	7082	3080	- slight heading change during run.
070454	R3-2	300/1	Nwd	CSD	7112	3091	
070727	R3-2	1/60	CW	CSD	7084	3024	
070845	R3-2	300/1	Zen	open	7023	3058	
07116	R3-2	300/1	Nwd	CSD	7012	3076	
071349	R3-2	1/60	CW	CSD	7107	3108	
071546	R3-2	300/1	Zen	open	7078	3084	Head to rearer run - data stopped
071816	R3-2	300/1	Nwd	CSD	7038	3069	
072054	R3-2	1/60	CW	CSD	7070	3056	
072211	R3-2	120/1	Zen	open	7018	3092	Heading change in run.
072318	R3-2	120/1	"	"	7026	3082	
072430	R3-2nd	1/60	CW	CSD	7102	3071	
074922	R4-1	1/60	CW	CSD	7123	305	
075237		1/60	CW	CSD	7056	3076	
075440	R4-1	600/1	Nwd	CSD	7006	3048	No guide wire manual start
080000	R4-1	1/60	CW	CSD	7042	3062	
080127	R4-1	600/1	Nwd	CSD			Overpass @ 0803 Z
080631	R4-1	1/60	CW	CSD	7126	3076	
080749	R4-1	600/1	Nwd	CSD	7067	3048	
081307	R4-1	1/60	CW	CSD	7072	3073	end of run
081926		1/60	CW	CSD	7111	3000	
081950	R4-2	300/1	Zen	open	7016	3041	FLSSO B-C.
082203	R4-2	300/1	Nwd	CSD	6996	3096	" "
082308	R4-2	1/60	CW	CSD	7067	3062	" "
082623	R4-2	300/1	Zen	open	7020	312	" "
082900	R4-2	300/1	Nwd	CSD	7101	3046	" "

ARIES flight log

Flight: B286 page 3 of 1

Date: 24/04/07 Operator(s): Joss Res: 1 Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: 1A21 HOUSTON B286

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
083138	R4-2	1/60	Cal	cls	7049	3067	
083257	R4-2	300/1	Zen	cls	7012	3064	
083529	R4-2	1/60	Cal	cls	7014	3052	end of run ^{4.2} @ FL350
083708	R4-3	300/1	Nad	cls	707	3059	leg windows open during perigee
083944	R4-3	1/60	Cal	cls	702	3039	
084102	R4-3	300/1	Zen	open	7011	3110	
084338	R4-3	300/1	Nad	cls	7061	3062	
084625	R4-3	1/60	Cal	cls	7067	3052	
084747	R4-3	300/1	Zen	open	7011	2969	
085021	R4-3	300/1	Nad	cls	7061	3052	
085253	R4-3	1/60	Cal	cls	708	3069	
085428	R4-4	300/1	Zen	open	6986	3048	FL350 sid 1
085703	R4-4	300/1	Nad	cls	7091	3054	
085936	R4-4	1/60	Cal	cls	7086	3049	
090052	R4-4	300/1	Zen	open	7039	3028	
090400	R4-4	300/1	Nad	cls	7042	3113	FL 350
090632	R4-4	1/60	Cal	cls	7066	3045	
090748	R4-4	200/1	Zen	open	6987	3193	
090941	R4-4	1/60	Cal	cls	703	3052	END of R4-4
091517	DATA OFF						

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	23/04/07	Flight	B286	log pages
Operator(s)	Chawn Harlow		Campaign	JIAVEX		
Departure	Ellington etd 1130L		Arrival	Ellington etd 0445L +2400		

**System start
MARSS**

Visual pod inspection						•
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						•
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						•
FERA on			at time	0307		
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	°C	Ch	°C	Ch18	°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on			at time			
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						•
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						•
Scanning on (LMD box)			at time	0308		
Scan indication		Monitor	•	Visual		•

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers	Not operated					
Turn on Deimos CPU						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Start Deimos Software			at time			
Initial target temperatures	Hot	297	Cold	297		
Target heating						
Scan indication		Monitor		Visual		
Weather	Cloud		Precip			
	Surface		Pressure			
	Other					

System functionality check (after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	0	at time	04:04:28		
Brightness temps 'sensible'						•
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344.6	Cold	297.8	
	Deimos:	Hot		Cold		
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B		
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)		
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20	
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)	
		32.5	37.6	39.7	40.9	

Power changeover

Headset on before start						•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.					•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)						•
Exit Deimos Software (x)						
POWER CHANGEOVER						
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton					•
Restart Deimos Software						
System running again			at time			

Flight:

B285

KEY

Not Fitted

Fitted, Not Operated

Duff Data

Minor Problems

OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nezvorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Report Created 26/06/2007
15:35:19

Misc Core

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Fax machine:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H:

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Last Updated:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

ADA:

CCN:

CDP:

CIP 100:

CIP 25:

CPI:

CVI:

SID1:

SID2:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC 3025 (AMS):

INC:

VACC:

CPC 3010A (CVI):

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR:

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

20/04/2007 17:40:57

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B286

Date: 24 April 2007

Instruments

1. CVI hygrometer no good in v. high RH (e.g. 98% as seen on B286)
2. Hiemann calcs funny again at high altitude see B284
3. Dry Neph zero not completed

Aircraft

Nil

Satcom-H Calls

Nil

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 23-24 April 2007

Flight No: B286

Pre-Flighter: BW

<u>Item</u>	<u>✓ or x</u>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	
<u>Aircraft Cabin</u>				
2	<input type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	Dry Drier impaded
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	<input type="checkbox"/>	Nezvorov	Checked and OFF	
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS	Checked	
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Align	
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	<input type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	? Dry
16	<input type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
17	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up	Jeff Brown
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	Night Flight
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC	ON & Checked	
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked	
23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
24	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hubs x 4	Checked ON	
25	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	& CB on Port Fwd SSP
26	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	
27	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	Set up	
28	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			

External Checks overleaf →

Pre-Flighter's Log

<u>Item</u> \checkmark or \times	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
<u>External</u>			
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	<i>Jane Bollen</i>
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> All other covers	Removed	
40	<input type="checkbox"/> Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
41	<input type="checkbox"/> Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	<input type="checkbox"/> Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>			<u>Signed</u>
43	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		<i>Night Flight</i>
44	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ICEX applied		
45	<input type="checkbox"/> Traps empty (weekly only)		

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B286:

Log	Reason
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
SWS	Not operated on this flight
FWVS	No log is taken for this FWVS
AMS	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	31 Aug 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

No Digital8 video recordings were made on this flight

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